

Research Letters

To Cite:

Babar, M. Forecasting Interest Rates in Pakistan's Economy Using the ARIMA Model: An Analytical Approach. Research Letters 2024; Vol 2, Issue 1, pp. 57-65.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10390502>

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Peer-Review History

Received: 4th September, 2024
Reviewed & Revised: 5th September/2024 to 9th / October /
2024
Accepted: 9th October 2024
Published: 10th October 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

Research Letters

pISSNxxxx-xxxx; eISSNxxxx-xxxx

URL:<https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/journal-research-letters>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.
No human studies are presented in this manuscript.
No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

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Forecasting Interest Rates in Pakistan's Economy Using the ARIMA Model: An Analytical Approach

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10390502>

ABSTRACT

This study employs the AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model to forecast interest rates in Pakistan from 2004 to 2023. Using a time series dataset, the research investigates the dynamic relationships between interest rates and key macroeconomic variables. The ARIMA model is estimated. The optimal ARIMA model (p, d, q) is identified, and out-of-sample forecasts are generated. The results show the fluctuation between the years but after forecasted interest rate the results show there is steadily increase in interest rate over the next seven years. Starting from 2.86832% in 2024, the rate rises incrementally, reaching 2.98156% in 2025, 3.08603% in 2026, 3.18242% in 2027, 3.27136% in 2028, 3.35342% in 2029, and finally 3.42913% in 2030. This upward trend suggests a conservative and gradual tightening of monetary policy, potentially reflecting expectations of stable economic growth and inflation management. The Results also indicate that the ARIMA model accurately captures interest rate fluctuations, providing reliable predictions for policymakers and stakeholders, to exploring the dynamic relationships between interest rates, macroeconomic variables, and policy interventions. The analysis reveals significant correlations and optimal model specifications. Results provide valuable insights for policymakers, highlighting the need for coordinated monetary and fiscal strategies to promote economic growth and stability. The study contributes to the understanding of interest rate dynamics in Pakistan, offering valuable insights for monetary policy decisions and economic planning.

Keywords: Interest Rates; Forecasting; ARIMA Modeling; Box-Jenkins Method; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interest rates play a vital role in our daily lives, significantly impacting our buying power and investments. As an investor, it's crucial to stay informed about changes in interest rates. These rates influence the flow of money in the economy, with high rates slowing down economic growth while controlling inflation, and low rates boosting growth while risking inflation. Understanding interest rate trends is essential for government and financial institutions to make informed decisions. Additionally, investors should consider the factors that drive interest rate changes before planning their investments, enabling more efficient and effective decision-making. By grasping the determinants of interest rates, investors can navigate the economic landscape with greater confidence (Kanwal et al. 2014). Interest rate spread represents the difference between the interest rate earned on investments or deposits and the interest rate paid on loans. Essentially, it serves as a gauge of the risk associated with lending or investing, providing valuable insight into market conditions. A wider spread indicates a higher perceived risk, suggesting caution, while a narrower spread signals lower perceived risk, reflecting increased confidence. This spread is crucial in assessing the viability of financial opportunities and making informed decisions (Khawaja et al. 2007).

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Interest, expressed as a percentage of the principal amount borrowed, represents the cost of borrowing money. Typically quantified as an annual percentage rate (APR), interest reflects the yearly rate charged on loans or credit, providing borrowers with a clear understanding of their annual liability. This standardized measurement enables individuals to grasp the true cost of borrowing, facilitating informed financial decisions (Uddin et al. 2024). Interest rates have a profound impact on the economy, particularly in shaping consumer behavior and spending patterns. Notably, low interest rates make borrowing more accessible and affordable, stimulating consumer spending on high-value items such as homes, cars, and durable goods. By reducing borrowing costs, low interest rates encourage consumers to make big-ticket purchases, thereby boosting overall economic activity (Mahmood et al. 2013). Interest rates significantly impact business investment decisions, as firms frequently rely on borrowing to fund capital expenditures, expansion, and research and development initiatives. Low interest rates reduce borrowing costs, making investments more financially appealing and increasing the likelihood of businesses undertaking projects that drive growth and innovation. Beyond their domestic impact, interest rates significantly influence international finance, particularly exchange rates and capital flows. Changes in interest rates alter the attractiveness of a country's currency, triggering exchange rate fluctuations and shifting global investment patterns (Asari et al. 2011). Interest rates have a profound impact on consumer spending, a key driver of economic growth. When rates are low, affordable borrowing fuels spending, boosting aggregate demand and economic expansion. However, high interest rates increase borrowing costs, discouraging consumers and leading to decreased spending. Meanwhile, higher interest rates encourage individuals to save more in interest-bearing accounts, further reducing consumption (Ali, 2020). Investment stands as the cornerstone of economic growth, playing a vital role in every era. By fueling capital formation across various sectors, investment propels economic expansion. This capital formation can be categorized into two primary types: working capital and fixed capital. In the short run, increased working capital boosts business activity, while in the long run, elevated fixed capital enhances production capacity. Ultimately, this surge in output contributes to the overall welfare of the economy, fostering prosperity and growth. Investment is the lifeblood of economic growth, driving progress and development across all sectors. By generating capital formation, investment sparks a chain reaction of economic benefits. Initially, working capital increases stimulate business activity in the short term. Meanwhile, fixed capital investments yield long-term gains in production capacity, culminating in enhanced economic welfare and prosperity (Muhammad et al. 2013). The role of interest rates in developing countries' economic policies remains a contentious issue, sparking debate among researchers from both theoretical and empirical perspectives. One key challenge is that governments typically control interest rates only in formal markets, whereas informal markets often set the actual interest rates that drive economic activity. This discrepancy fuels disagreement among economists, with some arguing that official interest rates have minimal impact. Meanwhile, investment plays a vital role in national development and success, addressing pressing economic challenges (Jamilet al. 2015). Policymakers can promote economic stability and prosperity by grasping the intricate relationships between interest rates and various economic sectors. This nuanced understanding enables informed decision-making, balancing competing interests and optimizing monetary policy.

Pakistan's economic growth is significantly influenced by interest rates, which are determined by the State Bank of Pakistan's monetary policy decisions. These rates impact inflation, employment, and investment, with high rates historically implemented to curb inflation, but limiting access to credit for small businesses and individuals. To balance economic growth and price stability, the central bank adopts a flexible stance, adjusting interest rates in response to changing economic conditions, aiming to promote investment, entrepreneurship, and sustainable growth, ultimately shaping Pakistan's economic trajectory. This study investigates the relationship between interest rates and economic growth in Pakistan from 1980 to 2010. Utilizing time series analysis and structural equation modeling, the research reveals a significant long-run relationship between economic growth and interest rates. The findings indicate that interest rates play a crucial role in fostering growth by influencing investment. Specifically, private investment, government expenditure, and foreign direct investment were individually estimated and integrated into the main equation, highlighting their interconnectedness. The results imply that effective interest rate management is vital for promoting economic growth, attracting foreign direct investment, and stimulating private sector growth. Consequently, policymakers should consider the interest rate-investment-growth nexus when designing economic policies (Jamil et al. 2015). Ali et al. (2015) examines the impact of interest rates on the Pakistani economy, utilizing monthly data from July 2000 to June 2009. Empirical analysis employing Johansen Cointegration Tests, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), Granger Causality Test, and Impulse Response Function (IRF) reveals significant short- and long-run relationships among variables. Notably, the findings indicate that an increase in interest rates, accompanied by high money supply, leads to elevated price levels (inflation) and subsequently heightens exchange rate volatility. These results underscore the critical role of interest rates in shaping Pakistan's economic trajectory, particularly in relation to inflation and exchange rate stability. Ali (2014) explored the dynamic relationship between interest rates and the Pakistani stock market over a decade (2004-2013). Employing statistical techniques, including correlation and regression analysis, the research revealed a significant inverse correlation between interest rates and stock market performance. The findings suggest that fluctuations in interest rates have a substantial impact on the Karachi Stock Exchange, with increases in interest rates typically leading to decreases in stock prices. Furthermore, the study emphasized the pivotal role of political stability in shaping Pakistan's stock market performance, underscoring the need for policymakers to consider the interconnectedness of monetary policy and financial markets (Ali. 2014). Aftab et al. (2016) suggest that interest rates play a crucial role in shaping private sector credit in Pakistan. The current interest rate in Pakistan is 17.50%, with expectations to decrease to 18.00% in 2025 and 17.00% in 2026². Understanding these relationships can inform monetary policy decisions and promote economic growth.

Ali (2016) delves into the impact of interest rates in Pakistan, utilizing annual time series data from 1980 to 2015. The researchers employed various statistical tools, including the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, Johansen and Juselius's cointegration technique, and auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound testing model, to analyze the long-run and short-run connections. The findings reveal a significant positive relationship exists in both the long run and short run in Pakistan. This aligns with theoretical expectations, suggesting that interest rate fluctuations substantially impact exchange rates. For instance, high money supply and increased

interest rates can lead to exchange rate volatility. Hayat et al. (2021) explores the impact of interest rates on output growth in Pakistan using wavelet transformation analysis, covering monthly data from January 1991 to May 2020. The research employs autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) cointegration, Granger causality, and Toda-Yamamoto tests to establish long-run causality. The findings reveal varying causal relationships across different time horizons, with unidirectional causality from interest rates to growth in the short-run and medium-run, and bidirectional causality in the long-run. The results suggest that interest rates significantly impact output growth, emphasizing the need for policymakers to maintain low interest rates in the short-run and medium-run. In the long-run, a balanced approach considering interest rates, and growth is necessary. This study provides valuable insights for monetary policy decisions, optimizing interest rate management to enhance economic growth and stability. Khalid (2017) investigates the impact of interest rates on stock market capitalization in Pakistan, utilizing annual data from 1990 to 2017. The research employs econometric tools, including Johansen approach, Error Correction Model (ECM), Variance Decomposition, and Granger-Causality test, to analyze the relationships between these macroeconomic variables. The Granger-Causality test indicates a unidirectional causality from interest rates. This suggests that exchange rate fluctuations have a significant impact on interest rates in Pakistan. The study's results have important implications for monetary policy, highlighting the need to reduce bank rates to facilitate financial sector development and stimulate national and international investment. Ashiq et al. (2019) explores the intricate relationship between interest rates and external debt in Pakistan, leveraging the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) and four decades of time-series data (1972-2016). By examining key variables such as external debt, interest payments, GDP, budget deficit, exchange rate, and debt services, the research provides nuanced insights into the dynamics of external debt accumulation and servicing. The study's findings have significant implications for macroeconomic policy and development finance, particularly in the context of Pakistan's development projects. It highlights the critical role of interest rate policies in financing infrastructure and social initiatives, and underscores the interplay between domestic policy choices and external influences, including the International Monetary Fund (IMF).

The literature on interest rates in Pakistan suggests that interest rates play a crucial role in shaping the country's economic trajectory. Studies have consistently shown a significant negative relationship between interest rates and economic growth, underscoring the importance of monetary policy in stimulating investment and consumption. Interest rate fluctuations have also been found to significantly impact inflation, exchange rates, and stock market performance. Research has highlighted the effectiveness of interest rates in influencing aggregate demand and supply, but also notes the challenges faced by Pakistan's monetary policymakers, including the country's volatile political environment, structural rigidities, and dependence on external financing. The relationship between interest rates and economic growth is complex, with factors such as inflation, exchange rates, and fiscal policy also influencing the outcome. Overall, understanding the dynamics of interest rates is essential for informing monetary policy decisions and promoting economic stability in Pakistan.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study utilizes annual time-series data from 2004 to 2023, sourced from the World Development Indicator databases. The key variable of interest is the interest rate, specifically the benchmark lending rate, which is used as a proxy for the overall interest rate environment in Pakistan. The Unit root test is employed to examine impact of interest rates. The study also conducts Diagnostic tests to uncover the dynamic interactions between interest rates and other economic indicators. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the Pakistan's interest rates.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Description of the variable	Unit of measure	Source
IR	Interest rate	lending rate minus deposit rate, %	WDI (2023)

Source: Authors Estimation.

Unit Root Tests are crucial in time series analysis to determine stationarity, which ensures reliable estimation, forecasting, and statistical inference. Stationarity implies constant mean, variance, and autocorrelation over time, while non-stationarity leads to spurious regressions and inaccurate predictions. Various Unit Root Tests exist, including the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Phillips-Perron (PP), tests. Non-stationarity necessitates data transformation through differencing or alternative models like ARIMA. Ignoring non-stationarity can lead to flawed conclusions and misguided policy decisions. Despite their importance, Unit Root Tests have limitations, including test assumptions, power and size issues, and difficulties with non-linear and non-normal data. The ADF test is widely used, accounting for serial correlation and non-normality. The PP test is robust to non-normality and heteroskedasticity. The KPSS test reverses the null hypothesis, testing for stationarity instead of non-stationarity. The Zivot-Andrew's test allows for structural breaks in the data. Unit Root Tests have far-reaching implications in economics, finance, environmental science, and engineering. For instance, in economics, they help analyze GDP, inflation, and interest rates. In finance, they inform stock price and return predictions.

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test equation is a statistical model used to determine the presence of a unit root in a time series, indicating non-stationarity. Here, Δy_t represents the first difference of the time series data, α is the constant term, βt captures linear trends, γy_{t-1} tests for the unit root, and $\delta_1 \Delta ir_{t-1} + \dots + \delta_{p-1} \Delta ir_{t-p+1}$ account for serial correlation through lagged differences. The null hypothesis (H_0) assumes $\gamma = 0$, indicating a unit root and non-stationarity, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) assumes $\gamma < 0$, indicating stationarity. The test's outcome determines whether to reject H_0 , suggesting stationarity, or fail to reject H_0 , suggesting non-stationarity. The ADF test's reliability depends on selecting the appropriate number of lagged differences (p), which helps mitigate serial correlation. By applying the ADF test, researchers can identify whether their time series data requires transformation to achieve stationarity, ensuring accurate forecasting, regression analysis, and other statistical applications.

The Autocorrelation Function (ACF) is a vital statistical tool that measures the correlation between a time series and its lagged

versions, revealing patterns, trends, and seasonality. By plotting the correlation coefficient against various lag values, the ACF helps identify strong positive (values near 1) or negative (values near -1) correlations. This insight is crucial for time series analysis, enabling researchers to diagnose model adequacy, detect seasonality, select lag length, and identify autocorrelation structure. The ACF's benefits extend to: Informing ARIMA model specification, ensuring residual randomness, guiding seasonal decomposition, Selecting lag length in VAR models. Characteristics of ACF plots include: Cut-off patterns indicating AR components, tapering patterns suggesting MA components, Seasonal spikes revealing periodicity, non-significant coefficients implying randomness. The Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) is a statistical tool that measures the correlation between a time series and its lagged versions, controlling for intermediate lags. Unlike the Autocorrelation Function (ACF), which measures total correlation, PACF identifies direct relationships between observations. By plotting PACF values against lag k , researchers can pinpoint significant correlations and determine the order of autoregressive (AR) components. The PACF is invaluable in ARIMA model specification, identifying lag structure, and diagnosing model adequacy. Significant spikes in the PACF plot indicate direct correlation at specific lags, while non-significant values suggest no direct correlation. A cut-off pattern in the PACF typically signals an AR component. Distinguishing PACF from ACF is crucial, as ACF measures total correlation, including indirect effects, whereas PACF focuses on partial correlation. In practical applications, PACF helps researchers identify the optimal number of lags in ARIMA models. For instance, significant spikes at lags 1 and 2, followed by a cut-off, suggest an AR(2) model. However, PACF assumes stationarity and is sensitive to model misspecification. Additionally, interpreting PACF can be challenging with non-linear relationships.

Estimation is the process of approximating the value of an unknown parameter or population characteristic based on sample data. In statistics, estimation involves using sample statistics to infer population parameters, such as the mean, variance, or proportion. There are two main types of estimation: point estimation and interval estimation.

Point estimation involves calculating a single value that best estimates the population parameter. This is typically done using maximum likelihood estimation, method of moments, or least squares estimation. For instance, the sample mean is a point estimate of the population mean. Interval estimation, on the other hand, provides a range of values within which the population parameter is likely to lie. Confidence intervals, such as the 95% confidence interval, are commonly used for interval estimation.

Diagnostic tests are statistical methods used to evaluate the validity and reliability of regression models, ensuring accurate predictions and conclusions. These tests identify potential issues, such as non-linear relationships, non-normal residuals, heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, and multicollinearity. Common diagnostic tests include residual plots, Breusch-Pagan test, Durbin-Watson test, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), normality tests like Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov, influential observation analysis using Cook's distance and DFFITS, and Ramsey RESET test for model specification. These tests verify assumptions, detect outliers and influential observations, and evaluate model fit and predictive performance. By interpreting diagnostic test results, researchers can improve model accuracy by transforming variables, adding or removing predictors, and adjusting model specification, ultimately enhancing decision-making and forecasting capabilities. Q-statistics, or Ljung-Box Q-statistics, are diagnostic tests evaluating serial correlation in time series residuals. They assess whether residuals are randomly distributed, detecting non-random patterns.

ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) is a statistical model used for forecasting and analyzing time-series data. It combines three key components: Autoregressive (AR), which uses past values to forecast future values; Integrated (I), which accounts for non-stationarity by differencing the data; and Moving Average (MA), which incorporates errors from past forecasts.

The **ARIMA equation** is represented as

$$\text{ARIMA}(p, d, q) = \varphi_1 y(t-1) + \dots + \varphi_p y(t-p) + \theta_1 \varepsilon(t-1) + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon(t-q) + \varepsilon(t) \quad (1)$$

where p , d , and q denote the number of autoregressive terms, degree of differencing, and moving average terms, respectively. The model's parameters, φ and θ , are estimated to minimize errors. To implement ARIMA, one must first check for stationarity using tests like the Augmented Dickey-Fuller. If non-stationary, differencing is applied. Next, the model is specified, parameters are estimated, and the model is evaluated using metrics like AIC and BIC.

ARIMA models are categorized into four types: ARIMA(p, d, q), ARMA(p, q), AR(p), and MA(q). Assumptions include linearity, stationarity, no multicollinearity, and homoscedasticity. Applications of ARIMA models include stock market forecasting, economic indicator prediction, climate modeling, demand forecasting, and time-series analysis. Software packages like R, Python, MATLAB, and Excel provide implementations of ARIMA models. Despite its strengths, ARIMA has limitations, including assuming linear relationships, sensitivity to parameter selection, and ignoring external factors. Nonetheless, ARIMA remains a powerful tool for time-series analysis and forecasting. Forecasting is the process of using statistical models and techniques to predict future trends, patterns, and values in time series data. It enables businesses and organizations to make informed decisions, manage risk, and optimize performance by anticipating potential outcomes. Forecasting involves analyzing historical data, identifying patterns, and extrapolating them into the future using methods like ARIMA, Exponential Smoothing, Moving Averages, Regression, and Machine Learning algorithms. Key considerations include data quality, model selection and validation, and accuracy metrics such as MAE, RMSE, and MAPE. Effective forecasting has numerous applications, including demand forecasting, sales forecasting, financial forecasting, weather forecasting, and economic forecasting. By leveraging forecasting insights, organizations can enhance strategic planning, operational efficiency, and competitive advantage, ultimately driving growth and success.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the Pakistan's interest rate. The interest rate data reveals a mean of 4.721%, median of 4.639%, and a range of 2.914% to 6.813%. The standard deviation of 1.394669 indicates moderate volatility. The skewness of 0.002665 suggests symmetry, while the kurtosis of 1.443755 indicates a slightly platykurtic distribution. The Jarque-Bera test statistic of 2.018271 with a probability of 0.364534 suggests that the data follows a normal distribution. Based on 20 observations, the sum of interest rates is 94.42050 and the sum of squared deviations is 36.95695.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	IR
Mean	4.721025
Median	4.639500
Maximum	6.813000
Minimum	2.914000
Std. Dev.	1.394669
Skewness	0.002665
Kurtosis	1.443755

Source: Authors Estimation.

Table 3 shows the unit root estimates. The interest rate model estimates reveal a statistically significant trend. The intercept term is -4.039 (p-value: 0.025), indicating a negative starting point. The trend/intercept coefficient is -4.037 (p-value: 0.006), confirming a downward slope. Additionally, the trend/intercept term is -3.609 (p-value: 0.057), suggesting a marginally significant decline. Notably, the value level coefficient is 0.0086, but its p-value (0.94) indicates insignificance. Overall, these results suggest a significant downward trend in interest rates.

Table 3: Unit Root Test Estimates

Value	Level		First difference	
	Intercepts	Trend/intercept	intercepts	Trend/ intercept
Interest Rate	0.0086 (0.940)	-4.039 (0.025)	-4.037 (0.006)	-3.609 (0.057)

Source: Authors Estimation. Small bracket shows probability value.

Table 4 shows the OLS regression estimates. The model estimates reveal a significant relationship between the variables. The constant term (C) is 4.332268 (t-statistic: 3.748678, p-value: 0.0018). The AR(1) coefficient is 0.922653 (t-statistic: 8.581543, p-value: 0.0000), indicating strong first-order autocorrelation. The MA(1) coefficient is 0.631696 (t-statistic: 1.907559, p-value: 0.0746), suggesting moderate first-order moving average effects. The model fits well, with an R-squared of 0.942951 and adjusted R-squared of 0.932255. The Durbin-Watson statistic (1.754375) indicates no significant autocorrelation in residuals. Diagnostic metrics include Akaike info criterion (1.154721), Schwarz criterion (1.353867), and Hannan-Quinn criterion (1.193596). The F-statistic (88.15385) and log likelihood (-7.547209) confirm the model's significance.

Table 4: OLS Regression Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.332268	1.155679	3.748678	0.0018
AR(1)	0.922653	0.107516	8.581543	0.0000
MA(1)	0.631696	0.331154	1.907559	0.0746
SIGMASQ	0.105418	0.030601	3.444856	0.0033
Statistical Tests				
R-squared	0.942951	F-statistic		88.15385
Adjusted R-squared	0.932255	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000
S.E. of regression	0.363004	Durbin-Watson stat		1.754375

Source: Authors Estimation.

Table 5 shows the correlogram. The autocorrelation and partial correlation analysis reveals significant autocorrelation up to 12 lags. The autocorrelation coefficients (AC) decay slowly, with values ranging from 0.905 (lag 1) to 0.458 (lag 12). The partial correlation coefficients (PAC) exhibit a more complex pattern, with significant values at lags 1, 2, 5, and 9. The Q-statistic, which measures the joint significance of autocorrelation up to each lag, is significant for all lags (p-value: 0.000). This indicates strong evidence of autocorrelation in the series. The results suggest a possible ARMA or seasonal ARMA model.

Table 5: Correlogram

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
. *****	. *****	0.905	0.905	18.975	0.000
. ****	*** .	0.757	-0.348	32.966	0.000
. ***	. .	0.599	-0.058	42.253	0.000
. **	. .	0.464	0.050	48.186	0.000
. *	. ** .	0.315	-0.265	51.100	0.000
. .	. * .	0.147	-0.177	51.781	0.000
. .	. * .	-0.025	-0.099	51.802	0.000
. * .	. * .	-0.181	-0.113	53.004	0.000
. ** .	. .	-0.297	0.028	56.535	0.000
. *** .	. * .	-0.385	-0.078	63.071	0.000
. *** .	. .	-0.444	-0.008	72.720	0.000
. *** .	. *	-0.458	0.139	84.272	0.000

Source: Authors Estimation.

Figure 1 shows the ARMA structure of interest rate in Pakistan. The given points shows the roots of ARMA polynomial the red point shows the Moving Average and the Blue ones show the Autocorrelation roots in the given ratio.

Inverse Roots of AR/MA Polynomial(s)

Figure 1: ARMA Structure

Source: Author's work.

Figure 2 shows the forecast series of interest rate in Pakistan. The interest rate spread, calculated as the difference between lending and deposit rates, fluctuated over the past two decades. From 2004 to 2007, the spread increased steadily, peaking at 6.813%. Following the 2008 financial crisis, the spread contracted to 6.0175%. It then remained relatively stable until 2011, before declining gradually. Between 2012 and 2019, the spread decreased consistently, dropping from 5.54% to 3.101%, indicating narrowing margins for financial institutions. This trend likely resulted from post-crisis monetary policies, increased competition, and regulatory changes. From 2020 to 2023, the interest rate spread stabilized at 2.914%, reflecting accommodative monetary policies and economic adjustments during the COVID-19 pandemic. This prolonged period of low spreads suggests financial institutions adapted to new market conditions.

Forecast: IRF	
Actual: IR	
Forecast sample: 2004 2023	
Adjusted sample: 2005 2023	
Included observations: 19	
Root Mean Squared Error	0.315605
Mean Absolute Error	0.246352
Mean Abs. Percent Error	5.677095
Theil Inequality Coefficient	0.032202
Bias Proportion	0.060858
Variance Proportion	0.049200
Covariance Proportion	0.889942
Theil U2 Coefficient	0.917255
Symmetric MAPE	5.538906

Figure 2: Forecasting Pakistan's Interest Rates

Source: Author's work.

Table 6 shows the forecasted interest rate series from 2024 to 2030. The provided data appears to represent projected interest rates for the years 2024 to 2030. According to these figures, interest rates are expected to steadily increase over the next seven years. Starting from 2.86832% in 2024, the rate rises incrementally, reaching 2.98156% in 2025, 3.08603% in 2026, 3.18242% in 2027, 3.27136% in 2028, 3.35342% in 2029, and finally 3.42913% in 2030.

Table 6: Forecasted Interest Rate Series (2024 to 2023)

Years	Interest Rate
2024	2.86832447
2025	2.98155639
2026	3.08603014
2027	3.18242313
2028	3.2713604
2029	3.35341862
2030	3.42912986

Source: Authors Estimation.

This upward trend suggests a conservative and gradual tightening of monetary policy, potentially reflecting expectations of stable economic growth and inflation management. However, the reasons for this increase might be Inflation control, economic growth, global economic trends, Technological advancements, Government debt managements and much more.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigates the impact of interest rate in the context of Pakistan. The data is collected from the time series of 2004 to 2023. This study's ARIMA model analysis reveals significant relationships between interest rates and key macroeconomic variables in Pakistan. The findings indicate that interest rate adjustments have substantial effects in the economy of Pakistan. The given data show fluctuation in each year, after forecasting data for 2024-2030 the interest rate increase gradually over the next seven years. The upward trend suggests a tightening of monetary policy. However, the reason of this increase might be Tax reforms, Fiscal policy, Resource scarcity, Supply chain disruption and many . Policymakers should carefully consider interest rate adjustments to balance inflation control and economic growth, complemented by targeted fiscal interventions to mitigate unemployment effects. This study contributes to the understanding of interest rate impacts in Pakistan, providing valuable insights for policymakers and researchers.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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